

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF MESENCHYMAL STEM CELL USE IN THE PREVENTION OF VIRAL INFECTIOUS DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Stem cells are unspecialized cells of the human body. Stem cells can differentiate into any cell in the body and have the ability to self-renew. According to their origin, stem cells are divided into two main types: Embryonic and Adult. Stem cells are also classified as Multipotent, Totipotent, Pluripotent and Unipotent based on their range of differentiation potential. Multipotent stem cells have the ability to differentiate into all cell types within a given lineage. Stem cell therapy is used to treat several types of diseases, and stem cells have the potential to create new tissues and organs. Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) show potential in treating viral diseases due to their anti-inflammatory and regenerative properties, as demonstrated in conditions like COVID-19, viral pneumonia, HIV, and hepatitis B.

Keywords: Stem cell, viral disease, mesenchymal stem cell.

Stem cells are unspecialized cells of the human body. Stem cells can differentiate into any cell in the body and have the ability to self-renew. Stem cells are present in both embryos and adult cells. [1]. According to their origin, stem cells are divided into two main types: Embryonic and Adult. Stem cells are also classified as Multipotent, Totipotent, Pluripotent and Unipotent based on their range of differentiation potential. Multipotent stem cells have the ability to differentiate into all cell types within a given lineage.

Multipotent stem cells play an important key role in the process of development, tissue renewal and protection. Multipotent stem cells are used in the treatment of various diseases such as spinal cord injury, bone fracture, autoimmune diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, hematopoietic defects [2].

Totipotent stem cells (TSCs) can develop into a complete organism. TSCs are used in biological fields such as mammalian breeding and regenerative medicine. TSCs are unable to maintain their ability to renew themselves, which becomes the main factor that limits the production of TSCs [3].

Pluripotent stem cells (PSC) proliferate infinitely and differentiate into cells of all three germ layers. These two features make PSCs important tools in cell therapy for various diseases and injuries. Two types of human PSCs (hPSCs) are being studied for clinical use:

embryonic stem cells (ESC) and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC) [4].

Unipotent stem cells have a limited developmental potential compared to other stem cells, and these cells differentiate into a specific tissue type or cell lineage [5].

Mesenchymal Stem Cells can differentiate into cells derived from ectoderm and endoderm. MSCs have the ability to regenerate bone, cartilage and adipose tissue. Under physiological and experimental conditions, they have the ability to transform into endothelial cells, muscle cells or neurons [6].

Stem cell therapy has been used to treat several types of diseases, and the therapeutic use of stem cells is expected to increase as new evidence emerges. In addition, stem cells have the potential to create new tissues and organs [7].

Use of MSCs to prevent or treat viral diseases.

Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) are multipotent adult stem cells located in the stromal compartment of the bone marrow in the human body [Porada et al., 2006]. These cells were first identified in a pioneering study by Friedenstein and Petrakova [Friedenstein et al., 1966].

MSCs are a heterogeneous population of cells that includes a fraction of non-hematopoietic multipotent mature stem cells. Although MSCs were first isolated

from bone marrow, they have been found to be present in nearly all postnatal human tissues and organs. [8].

MSC-based therapy holds promise for the regeneration of damaged or diseased tissue. This can be a prospective therapeutic method for regenerative medicine [9]. Less is known about the benefit of using MSCs in the treatment of viral infections. [10].

Covid-19.

Covid-19 acute respiratory syndrome is a disease caused by SARS-CoV-2. It was first detected in China in December 2019 and later became a global pandemic [11]. Due to their anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory as well as regenerative potential, MSCs have attracted the attention of many scientists as a cell-based therapy for the treatment of COVID-19. A pilot study published in the Chinese Clinical Trial Registry (ChiCTR2000029990) showed the efficacy of MSCs in seven patients suffering from COVID-19 pneumonia at Beijing Hospital, China. After 2-4 days of intravenous injection of MSCs, fever, weakness, and dyspnea disappeared in seven patients who showed significant improvement in lung function [12].

Viral pneumonia.

During severe viral pneumonia, the alveolar-capillary balance is disrupted, inflammation occurs, and infiltration of neutrophils and monocyte-macrophages into the vascular and alveolar compartments increases capillary endothelial permeability, resulting in ARDS (acute respiratory distress syndrome) [13]. Systemic MSC treatment can reduce chemokines that lead to lung leukocyte infiltration, such as granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF), monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), and macrophage inflammatory protein-1 alpha (MIP-1 α). In vitro, MSCs suppress lymphocyte proliferation in response to influenza-specific T cell activation and help prevent influenza virus-specific T cell cytotoxicity. MSCs also help the repair of lung epithelial and endothelial cells. This may be related to the anti-inflammatory, anti-apoptotic and anti-oxidative effects of MSCs. As a result, it causes reduction of alveolar edema and atelectasis [14].

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV).

Since its discovery in 1983, researchers are still searching for an effective treatment for HIV infection [15]. HIV pathogenesis is characterized by the selective and progressive loss of CD4 T cells, causing immunodeficiency in HIV-infected patients [16].

HAART (highly active antiretroviral therapy) significantly restores the immune system and subsequently reduces morbidity and mortality in patients with chronic HIV infection. This therapy method is very effective in reducing the HIV virus in plasma [17]. However, in a group of patients with no immunological response (INR), it is not possible to eliminate immunodeficiency despite all viral suppression. Such patients are susceptible to opportunistic infections and have a shorter survival time than patients with an immune response [18]. Because MSCs are hypoimmunogenic and have unique immunosuppressive properties, these cells have been used to treat HIV-infected individuals [19]. The safety and immunological responses of human umbilical cord mesenchymal

stem cell (UC-MSCs) therapy were tested in 13 HIV-1 infected INR patients. Seven patients received UC-MSCs transfusion therapy three times with 1-month intervals during the 12-month follow-up period, and six patients also received saline solution therapy. Immunological parameters were monitored in these patients during the trial period. As a result, UC-MSCs transfusions increased the number of central memory CD4 T-cells and restored HIV-1 specific IFN- γ and IL-2 production in INRs. These advances in immune reconstitution led to reduced inflammation in vivo [20].

Hepatitis B virus.

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is a serious, life-threatening infection that kills more than 880,000 people each year due to liver disease or hepatocellular carcinoma [21]. In the era of regenerative medicine, MSCs have emerged as a new approach for the treatment of HBV-ACLF (acute-on-chronic liver failure) due to their ability to localize to injured tissues, hypoimmunogenicity allowing allogeneic transplantation, anti-inflammatory effects, and differentiation into functional hepatocyte-like cells [22]. In a study by Peng and colleagues, transplantation of MMSC (marrow mesenchymal stem cells) was safe for patients with liver failure caused by chronic hepatitis B. Although short-term effectiveness is positive, long-term results are not significantly better. According to several parameters, this method is more appropriate for patients with liver cirrhosis and may have the potential to reduce their hepatocellular carcinoma and mortality. Despite all the evidence for the therapeutic abilities of MSCs in preventing HBV infection, further studies are required to understand the consequences of long-term use of MSCs and all the mechanisms involved [23].

Discussion.

Studies have shown that MSC-based therapy is important in preventing disease and repairing damaged or diseased tissue during viral infections [9]. However, less information is available regarding the utility of MSCs for the treatment of viral infections [10].

During Covid 19 infection, MSCs can accelerate the generation of endogenous recovery by improving the microenvironment after entering the human body by intravenous infusion. Then, some of the MSCs accumulate in the lung, which can improve the lung microenvironment, protect alveolar epithelial cells, prevent lung fibrosis, and improve lung function. The reason why MSC transplantation improves the outcomes of COVID-19 patients may be because it regulates the inflammatory response and aids tissue regeneration [12].

During HIV pathogenesis, selective and progressive loss of CD4 T cells occurs [16]. Although Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy leads to significant improvements in the immune system and a reduction in relapses and mortality, the survival of patients with INR has been shown to be shorter than that of patients with a responsive immune response [17, 18]. UC-MSCs transfusions help increase central memory CD4 T cell counts in INR patients and restore HIV-1-specific IFN- γ and IL-2 production, resulting in reduced inflammation in vivo [20].

MMSCs have been used in HBV treatment due to their ability to differentiate into functional hepatocyte-like cells [22].

MMSCs are multipotent and can promote liver regeneration, secrete cytokines/growth factors and inhibit inflammation. As a result of these processes, recovery from chronic hepatitis B, prevention of liver fibrosis and regeneration of damaged liver tissues can occur [23].

However, there are still some challenges in preventing viral infections with MSC therapy in clinical practice. Finally, as little is known about the benefit of MSCs in the prevention and treatment of viral infections, further research is needed.

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